

INTEGRATION WITH THE DEVELOPMENT SECTOR IN IMPROVING SAFETY MANAGEMENT IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

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Abstract: The 21st century is the age of technology and development, so it is wrong to raise children and prepare them for life, as in the previous era. At a time when life is accelerating, children expect the right education and upbringing in accordance with this speed and flow. In particular, the PEI educator is responsible for properly instilling safety in children, which is now considered important. For this reason, future educators need understand meaning of "Safety Management". It is in the World System of Preschool Education that one can see this management and feel the technology of its instillation in children. In addition, in our country, in order to form the ability of preschoolers to create their own security, PEI teachers require great skill and competence of educators. Also necessary for the correct formation of this area among future educators are considered various didactic games, literature, teaching aids, which will greatly help in the formation of the "Child Safety Management". Another important system is the formation and improvement of the security system. This system looks like this: component, element, stage, task, goal, content, form, means, principle, pedagogical conditions of learning. In addition, the system of learning safety as behavior can be seen in different processes. For example, educational process, pedagogical process, learning process, learning process, safety course learning process, etc. "Pedagogical process" is an important stage in the organization of preschool education. The pedagogical process is taken as the main goal in the formation of a culture of safe behavior, adaptation processes.

Keywords: safety, management, children, domain sphere, "Physical and health" sphere, nature, methods, game, interactive, observation, difference, curriculum, development.

Annotatsiya: XXI asr texnologiya va taraqqiyot asri, shuning uchun oldingi davrdagidek bolalarni tarbiyalash, ularni hayotga tayyorlash noto'g'ri. Hayot jadallashib borayotgan bir davrda bolalar ana shu tezlik va oqimga mos ravishda to'g'ri ta'lim va tarbiya kutadi. Xususan, MTT o'qituvchisi bolalarda xavfsizlikni to'g'ri singdirish uchun javobgardir, bu hozir muhim hisoblanadi. Shu sababli, bo'lajak o'qituvchilar "Xavfsizlikni boshqarish" tushunchasini tushunishlari kerak. Butunjahon maktabgacha ta'lim tizimida bunday boshqaruvni ko'rish va uni bolalarga singdirish texnologiyasini his qilish mumkin. Bundan tashqari, mamlakatimizda maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarning o'z xavfsizligini yaratish qobiliyatini shakllantirish uchun PEI o'qituvchilari

tarbiyachilardan katta mahorat va malakani talab qiladi. Bo‘lajak o‘qituvchilarda ushbu sohani to‘g‘ri shakllantirish uchun turli xil didaktik o‘yinlar, adabiyotlar, o‘quv qo‘llanmalari ham zarur bo‘lib, ular "Bolalar xavfsizligini boshqarish" ni shakllantirishda katta yordam beradi. Yana bir muhim tizim xavfsizlik tizimini shakllantirish va takomillashtirishdir. Bu tizim quyidagicha ko‘rinadi: komponent, element, bosqich, vazifa, maqsad, mazmun, shakl, vosita, printsip, o‘qitishning pedagogik shartlari. Bundan tashqari, o‘quv xavfsizligi tizimini xulq-atvor sifatida turli jarayonlarda ko‘rish mumkin. Masalan, ta’lim jarayoni, pedagogik jarayon, o‘quv jarayoni, o‘quv jarayoni, xavfsizlik kursini o‘rganish jarayoni va boshqalar "Pedagogik jarayon" maktabgacha ta’limni tashkil etishning muhim bosqichidir. Xavfsiz xulq-atvor madaniyatini, moslashish jarayonlarini shakllantirishda pedagogik jarayon asosiy maqsad sifatida qabul qilinadi.

Kalit so‘zlar: xavfsizlik, boshqarish, bolalar, domen sohasi, “Jismoniy va salomatlik” sohasi, tabiat, usullar, o‘yin, interaktiv, kuzatish, farq, o‘quv dasturi, rivojlanish.

Аннотация: 21 век – век технологий и развития, поэтому неправильно воспитывать детей и готовить их к жизни, как в предыдущую эпоху. В то время, когда жизнь ускоряется, дети ожидают правильного образования и воспитания в соответствии с этой скоростью и течением. В частности, воспитатель ДОО отвечает за правильное привитие детям безопасности, что сейчас считается важным. По этой причине будущим воспитателям необходимо понимать значение «Управления безопасностью». Именно в Мировой системе дошкольного образования можно увидеть это управление и прочувствовать технологию его привития детям. Кроме того, в нашей стране для формирования у дошкольников умения создавать собственную безопасность педагогам ДОО требуется большое мастерство и компетентность воспитателей. Также необходимыми для правильного формирования этого направления у будущих воспитателей считаются различные дидактические игры, литература, методические пособия, которые во многом помогут в формировании «Управления безопасностью ребенка». Еще одной важной системой является формирование и совершенствование системы безопасности. Эта система выглядит следующим образом: компонент, элемент, этап, задача, цель, содержание, форма, средство, принцип, педагогические условия обучения. Кроме того, систему безопасности обучения как поведения можно рассматривать в различных процессах. Например, образовательный процесс, педагогический процесс, учебный процесс, процесс обучения, процесс обучения по курсу безопасности и т. д. «Педагогический процесс» является важным этапом в организации дошкольного образования. Педагогический процесс принимается за основную цель в формировании культуры безопасного поведения, адаптационных процессов.

Ключевые слова: безопасность, управление, дети, предметная область, область «Физическое и здоровье», природа, методы, игра, интерактивность, наблюдение, различие, учебная программа, развитие.

Introduction

Currently, many efforts are being made to find a solution to the preschool education system and its problems. First of all, the President's personal interest and initiative to improve the preschool education system has determined how important this field is. Because we know that preschool age is the most important and most difficult period. In this period, cooperation between parents and educators is very important. At the same time, child safety is considered as the biggest and necessary factor for preschool education organization. During the years, there have been a lot of changes in

ministry of Preschool and School education of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The cooperation with foreign company and organizations help to develop and improve our preschool educational organizations. Like for instance, meeting the Ambassador Extraordinary and Plenipotentiary of the Republic of Korea in Uzbekistan Mr. Kim Hee San on February 13, 2023. The main purpose of meeting was The Korean side expressed readiness to make all efforts for the successful implementation of joint projects in the field of preschool education, in particular, united projects such as the "Comprehensive Center for Training and Qualification of Personnel and Construction of an Innovative State Preschool Education Organization in Tashkent" implemented in cooperation with KOICA. And other example is cooperation with university Bucheon in Korea.¹ We know that there are similarities between the Uzbek preschool education system and the Korean preschool education system. For this reason, we will examine how the safety sector has developed in the Korean education system and the differences.

The KICCE Early Childhood Observation Scale developed by the Korea Institute of Child Care in 2019, comprises 59 observation items across five domains to assess children`s knowledge, skills, and attitudes during play and daily activities in preschool and daycare centers. This tool aids teachers in understanding children`s development based on the revised Nuri Curriculum. Each observation item is supplemented with examples to facilitate comprehension, emphasizing that these item are not age-specific achievement standards but reference materials for understanding children. The scale supports a structured approach to evaluating physical health, motor skills, and hygiene practices among preschoolers, promoting active participation and self-care behaviors. There are a lot of similarity with The KICCE and “Ilk qadam” (First Step) program, especially, the domain factor is “Physical and Health activity”. For example, some aspects of safety are adressed within other domains: “Daily Life”. This item observes a child`s progression in independently managing tasks, which can relate to safety in the sense of self-sufficiency and responsible behavior, such as cleaning up after themselves.² The “First Step” program also focuses on steps and hygiene. Especially in the winter season, weekly topics are allocated on how to distinguish clothes and pay attention to health. , natural changes begin in February and continue until April.³ However, there are some issues about methods of safety management.

Methods

This very factor indicates how much the child should know and follow **the rules of safety**. However, the use of conversation and different picture cards is not effective nowadays. For this reason, it can be good to carry out safety rules by topic. For example, teaching safety to students with the integration of development centers.

We know that the best method of activity for children is a game. During the game, children do not feel any pressure or fatigue as if they are being taught. If children learn the movement within the frame of a game, they will learn the subject faster and have a greater chance of remembering it.

If the play and development centers are combined in carrying out safety activities, the child will not think of this direction as separate. One of them, we can consider several directions given in the "Nuri" program of the Republic of Korea.

¹ [MPE.UZ | Maktabgacha va maktab ta’limi vazirining birinchi o’rinbosari Agrippina Shin Koreya Respublikasining O’zbekistondagi Favqulodda va muxtor Elchisi janob Kim Xi San bilan uchrashdi](https://mpe.uz)

² The KICCE 2019

³ “First Step” program, updated version 2022

“Sexual violence and child abuse prevention education”, so of course this theme can be unnecessary but we know that time children can interested opposite gender. (Theory of Freud) [7-12]

Certainly, there is some main concepts to know:

1. Knowing my body is precious
2. Cultivating an attitude of respect for the body of you and your friends
3. Interested in how to protect my body.
4. Sharing your thoughts about physical contact
5. Knowing the names of body parts.⁴

So, in this topic we can integrate with developmental area “Speech development”. There is some technologies to teach children:

- **“Good feeling and bad feeling”**

In this technology, children are interviewed and the teacher asks the children through pictures. In this technology, it is explained that children can take care of their body and that it is impossible to hold all parts of the body. For example: "If my father or mother hugs me..." - this good feeling.

"If my friend touches me or wants to see my private parts..." - this bad feeling.

Through this technology, it is possible to explain and teach children the need to protect all parts of the body, along with understanding their own value as a person.

- **"Don't touch, don't see, I don't want"**

In this technology, it is possible to strengthen the activity given above, that is, in this method, various pictures are shown to the child, and in unpleasant situations, the children say "Touch! Do not see! I don't want to!" they say. In this way, children can be taught to understand their feelings and appreciate them as individuals. [8-10p]

- **"Let's wear our clothes!"**

We give the children body painting and different clothes. In this, children's underwear, outerwear, and shoes are provided. Children put on clothes in order. This game can also teach children how to wear clothes in technology. Children should also be taught hygiene, and it is the most paramount form this habit, especially for 6-7 year olds. Before going to school, children should acquire these habits and be able to apply them to independent life.

- **O/X game**

Children are asked various questions by the teacher, and if they are correct, they are asked to go to O, that is, correct, and X if they are incorrect. It is appropriate if it is played as a technology strengthening game. Because it is possible to talk with the children about the topic and conduct the activity as a final and reinforcing activity.

The following questions can be asked in this activity:

- - "When I play with my friend, I can show my private part" Answer: X
- - "I should tell my parents or teacher when I feel uncomfortable" Answer: O
- - "My friend's body is just as valuable as my body" Answer: O
- - "When the day is hot, it is okay not to wear underwear" Answer: X
- - I say, "If someone wants to touch my body, I don't want to." Answer: O
- - "My friend can see my underwear while playing hospital" Answer: X
- - "I will not touch or see my friend's private body part" Answer: O

[10-13p]

- **Prevention education of disappearance/abduction**

⁴ 어린이집 안전공제회 Childcare center Safety& Insurance Association

Key safety concepts:

- They understand situations in which they can get lost, and can ask for help when lost.
- Be wary of strangers and know how to ask for help.
- I know my name and guardian's name and phone number

Family connection:

- In case of missing/kidnapped prevention education, share the relevant information with guardians through notice boards (kids notes, etc.).
- Making a safety notebook: “Remember your name and phone number” is a family-linked material that can be used at PEI. Send it home and write it with your guardian.

We can take this topic with children in the center of story-role games and staging. A fairy tale book or a multimedia exhibition can be used for this purpose. First of all, a book is read to the children or shown through a multimedia tool, and a conversation is held with the children. The characters conduct the events in the form of a conversation, and then the educator explains to the children how important it is to remember names and phone numbers. The participation of parents during the activity is very effective.

In this case, parents can participate at home or in a preschool education organization and tell the phone numbers to the children. Or, in a preschool educational organization, children and educators can ask for names or phone numbers in a role-playing game.

- **Guess in order**

In this method, children are given different cards and asked to find their sequence. This method helps children to feel the plot visually. In this case, the most helpful situation is the signs of **stopping, thinking, and asking for help.**

At the same time, when a stranger comes and says, "**Go, I'll take you there,**" he has to attract the public by saying, "**No, I don't want to!**", "**Help me.**"

All this method is carried out through cards. Before carrying out this activity, children are introduced to the topic through a video exhibition and fairy-tale books and are introduced to the activity. During the activity, children can be asked their opinions in a question-and-answer mode, and interest in the process can be aroused.

- **Health and hygiene management education of infectious diseases and drugs, prevention of misuse, etc.**

Key safety concepts:

* To prevent infectious diseases, we know that personal hygiene (hand washing, brushing teeth, etc.) must be thoroughly practiced.

* Learn how to properly wash your hands.

* I take out medicine carelessly, and know the miraculous ham with dose and usage.

- **Bubble Team vs Germ Team**

Glue the picture of the Bubble Witch and Germ Witch to the front and back of the thick plate. The team that flips the board to reveal more pictures before the time runs out wins.

- **How to avoid catching a cold?**

It is appropriate to carry out this activity in the art center, after giving information that this activity should be healthy and not sick, small books will be made. The topic is "Don't you want to get sick?" It is called, and if you don't want to get sick, you should do these things. The teacher helps the children to make a book, and the picture can be taken out or drawn by the children to make it into a book.

In this activity mainly:

"If you don't want to get sick, you should pay attention to your health!"

"Get enough sleep"

"The right distribution of food"

"Wash often"

"Wash your hands clean"

"Brush teeth cleanly"

Important factors in this case will be shown in the booklet.

In order to properly form the skill of washing hands, children are encouraged to imagine how to wash their hands through a picture. For this, a sequence of pictures is shown, and children perform the sequence in an exercise position together with children. Then, in arrange to propel the children, at each stage that is done correctly, they are given the chance to draw a picture of the bubbles or stick a sticker on them, and whoever has the most bubbles is encouraged.

- **“Find necessary pill”**

This method can be completed by showing the multi-video to the children, asking questions by the teacher and distributing the cards correctly. In this case, it is important to carefully observe the video characters and remember what kind of medicine they need. Also, it is considered necessary for the educator to explain that it is not allowed to drink or touch the drugs without the permission of an adult. For example, it is important to show that medicines are not candy or sweets, and that if they are consumed without question, they will cause great harm. Children should understand well that medicines are not toys, they should know that they can drink and eat only when they are sick, when their parents or guardians give them to them. [24-30p]⁵

Results

Using the integrated safety education methods can yield several positive outcomes for children. By incorporating safety concepts into play and development activities, children are more likely to internalize and remember crucial safety rules without feeling pressured. This approach helps them understand the importance of personal boundaries, safe interactions, and appropriate responses in various situations.

Specifically, integrating activities like the “Good feeling and bad feeling” exercise can enhance children’s ability to recognize and articulate uncomfortable or unsafe situations, empowering them to protect themselves from potential harm. Similarly, role-playing scenarios focused on abduction prevention can equip children with skills to seek help and avoid dangerous interactions with strangers. Furthermore, teaching health and hygiene through engaging games like “Bubble Team and Germ Team” or creating personalized books on preventing colds can foster good hygiene habits from a young age. These habits are essential for preventing the spread of infectious diseases and promoting overall well-being. By using interactive methods, educators can create a supportive learning environment where children feel comfortable asking questions and expressing their concerns. The O/X game and questions and sessions can serve as reinforcing activities, ensuring that children grasp key concepts and can apply them in real-life scenarios. Ultimately, the integration, confident, and resilient children who are better prepared to navigate potential risks and protect their health and safety.

⁵ 어린이집 안전공제회 Childcare center Safety & Insurance Association

Discussion

In general, safety in preschool educational organizations is present in all areas, but we believe that it needs to be approached more deeply. In particular, the child should have a deep understanding of his body and have fundamental skills in medicine. Children should also know how to talk to strangers and how to deal with them and ask for help. Safety areas such as hygiene and healthy lifestyles, nature, etc. are covered in the First Step program, but there are still areas of safety that need to be addressed. In particular, “Talking with strangers” and what to do when a “Child is left at home” are a bit of a question.

It is possible to conduct activities for children not only in conversation and video exhibition, but also in a practical situation at present.

Also:

- Parental cooperation;
- Bringing activities and technologies that develop visual memory to children;
- To carry out the rules and activities in an age-appropriate manner when separated into subjects;
- Constantly introduce the concept of safety into the process;
- The educator should be able to form factors such as the child's own body, attention to hygiene, the ability to identify and perform what tasks he should perform when he feels danger.